

Tourism-led Poverty Alleviation in South Asia – An Analytical Rapportage

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Abstract:

Presently, when the whole world is busy celebrating the technological advancements, accumulated wealth and gains from globalization along with industrialization, poverty continues to stand as a ubiquitous and prevalent predicament in South Asia which is home to a quarter of the world population and nearly one third of the poor people in the world. Albeit, there has been a sizeable reduction in the poverty headcount ratio since 1990, about 256 million people remain in absolute poverty in this region. Inequality both in social (*e.g. gender, social strata and standard of living*) and economical (*e.g. per head income, Gini index and wealth distribution*) terms is adding fuel to fire. However, the region has shown tremendous progress in tourism thanks to its natural, manmade and cultural endowments. In this paper, the authors have argued that tourism has predominant predicaments to be the panacea for poverty in South Asia. Tourism-led poverty alleviation studies have mostly been carried out in South East Asian context and this paper can bridge this gap. Various initiatives, policies and measures aimed at poverty alleviation through tourism have been highlighted in this paper.

Key Words: Poverty, South Asia, Development and Socio-Economic Factors, Inequality.

[1] INTRODUCTION

Poverty is one of the most distressful and disturbing condition which poses serious challenges to the development of the world (Mohanty, Chandran & Gantait, 2015). George Bernard Shaw (1907), in the preface of his masterly work Major Barbara, mentions "*The greatest of evils and the worst of crimes is poverty.*" On the centenary year of this fabulous play, Amartya Sen (2007) affirmed Shaw's comment from the economic perspective. In the epilogue of his work 'Poverty, evil

and crime' Sen states "So I end by affirming that George Bernard Shaw was right, a hundred years ago today ..."

The issues with regards to poverty and the ways it can be solved still remain an acute agenda in the global development debate (Andley et al., 2009). The UN General Assembly (2015) acknowledges that poverty alleviation is the most vital challenge faced by the world and is an indispensable prerequisite to sustainable development most specifically because even though the poverty head count ratio has reduced by a large amount, poverty is still a global phenomenon as 767 million (10.7% of the global population) live below the international poverty line of US\$1.90/day by the year 2013 (World Bank, 2016). Mohanty, Chandran & Gantait (2015) argues that poverty agenda is still more critical in South Asia which is a home to 33% (256 million) of the world's poorest people (World Bank, 2016) and nearly 15% of the South Asian population lived under the poverty line of US\$1.90/day in 2013 (Ortiz & Roser, 2016). All these statistics in the background establishes that poverty has become a matter of concern in South Asian context.

Since 1960, tourism has been recognized as a catalyst in case of sustainable development that can even eradicate poverty especially in developing countries. Ashley, Boyd & Goodwin (2000) for the very first time, recommended tourism as a prospective tool to fight against poverty though they criticized the tourism stakeholders for excessive concern for investment and infrastructure development while, negligence over more important aspect i.e. if tourism development is being able to unlock the opportunities and fulfill the needs of the poor or not. Ashley, Goodwin & Roe (2001) proposes to incorporate the 'bottom-up' approach in tourism to enhance the scope for the poor. Jamieson et al. (2004) suggest that mainstream tourism should move beyond the 'Trickledown Theory' and it should emphasize on creating 'Net Benefits' for the poor. Zhao & Ritchie (2007) advocate for more participation of poor in tourism as according to them, once these poor can access to the economic opportunity, they can even change their destiny. Moreover, studies have identified that, active participation from host community (Brohman, 1996; Tosun, 2000; Cole, 2006; Chok et al., 2007), sense of ownership, involvement and leadership in decision making process (Brohman, 1996; Tosun, 2000; OCDE, 2005; Scheyvens, 2007), opportunity in commercial viability and market penetrability (Alsop & Heinsohn, 2005; Harrison, 2008), community empowerment (Eade 1997; Schilcher, 2007), equity and justice (Schilcher, 2007; Harrison, 2008), easy access to information, knowledge share, communication and community capacity building (White, 2004; Cooper, 2006; Romanow & Bruce, 2006; Shaw & Williams, 2009; Sheate & Partidário, 2010), network (Novelli et al. 2006), safety and security (Hall & Brown, 2006), good governance (Brohman, 1996; Scheyvens, 2007; Schilcher, 2007; Dinica, 2009) etc. are some of the major determinants for tourism to contribute to poverty alleviation. Lemma (2014) divulged that tourism has greater benefit to the economy of smaller nations although the relative importance is greater for particular countries. Therefore, many developing nations including the South Asian countries (Nepal, Bhutan, Sri Lanka,

India, Bangladesh, Pakistan, Maldives and Afghanistan) are trying to eradicate poverty by promoting tourism through various tourism ventures.

[2] Study Objectives

This study revolves around two objectives. The first one is to give an overview of the current profile of poverty in Southern region of Asia and trace out various intrinsic factors associated with poverty. The 2nd and final objective is to highlight how tourism is becoming one of many remedial plans in poverty alleviation and tourism initiatives in last few decades have been strengthening the foothold of the poverty stricken people in most of the South Asian countries. While, most of the Asian studies on tourism led poverty elimination topic are restricted in South East Asia, the authors feel that this paper can be handy for future research in South Asian context.

[3] Research Methodology

This paper is purely secondary in nature and it tries to add few insights to the existing knowledge base of tourism led poverty alleviation. The data for this paper were collected from various journals, newspaper cuttings, Government and private documents and media reports. Content analysis method was then applied to bring out logical coherence in the writing. Both quantitative and qualitative data were highlighted. The study will fall in descriptive research design approach.

[4] Poverty: ubiquitous Problem in South Asia

Poverty is a perennial problem in the South Asian region which constitutes Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Bhutan, Maldives, Nepal, India, Pakistan, and Sri Lanka. About 24.8% of the world population dwells in South Asia (**World Population Meters, 2016**), of which above 15% stay below poverty line (2nd highest poverty/head ratio) which constitutes 33% of the world poor (**Ortiz & Roser, 2016**). Even with such a high presence of population the region's contribution to World GDP is little more than 3.5% which is abysmally low. (**Table I**)

Table I

Countires	GDP contribution	GDP Contribution (%)
India	2,073,543	2.821
Pakistan	269,971	0.367
Bangladesh	195,079	0.265
Sri Lanka	82,316	0.112
Nepal	20,881	0.028
Afghanistan	19,199	0.026
Maldives	3,143	0.004
Bhutan	1,962	0.003
South Asia	2,666,094	3.627
World	73,502,341	100

Source: - World Bank, 2016

Table II depicts that the South Asian region has the least percentage of urban population that highlights that most of the people live in rural areas that lack even the basic facilities commonly available in urban setups. However, the median age of the region falls around 26, which implies that most of people are youth those are readily available for acquiring jobs. But the infrastructure for developing skill of this young mass still remains highly contesting phenomena. Therefore, the region is suffering from issue like unemployment that is adding up to the misery.

Table II

World Population Distribution							
#	Region	Population -2016	Density (P/Km ²)	Area (Km ²)	Med. Age	Urban Pop %	World Share
1	Southern Asia	1,846,767,481	289	6,399,056	26	34.70%	24.80%
2	Eastern Asia	1,618,777,725	140	11,562,698	38	62%	21.80%
3	Rest of Asia	970,679,267	220	13,068,373	27	52.5%	13.00%
4	Africa	1,216,129,815	41	29,661,703	19	40.20%	16.40%
5	Europe	738,849,002	33	22,121,228	42	74.30%	9.90%
6	Latin America*	641,029,306	32	20,158,154	29	79.50%	8.60%
7	Northern America	360,529,324	19	18,680,276	38	82.60%	4.90%
8	Oceania	39,901,355	5	8,489,650	33	70.80%	0.50%

Source: - World Population Meters, 2016 and * implies including the Caribbean

As poverty is a multidimensional concept it has no absolute definition. However, poverty has been mostly described through economic and social indicators. Therefore, the authors have made an effort to provide a broader picture of poverty by tabular representation of various indicators for the South Asian countries.

Table -III

Attribute	Afghanistan	Bangladesh	Bhutan	India	Maldives	Nepal	Pakistan	Sri Lanka
% of people living below \$1.90 a day (2011)	n.a.	18.5	2.2	21.2	7.3	15	7.9	1.9
% of people living below \$3.10 a day	n.a.	56.8	13.3	58	23.3	48.4	43.6	14.6
Gini Index	27.82 (2008)	32.12 (2010)	38.73(2012)	33.90(2010)	37.37 (2004)	32.82(2010)	29.63(2011)	36.40 (2010)
Unemployment (2013)	8	4.3	2.1	3.6	11.6	2.7	5.1	4.2
Life Expectancy atBirth Total (2012)	60.51	70.29	67.89	66.21	77.57	67.98	66.44	74.07
Life Expectancy atBirth Female (2012)	61.81	71.08	68.23	68	78.65	69.13	67.34	77.24
Life Expectancy atBirth Male (2012)	59.27	69.55	67.56	64.5	76.55	66.89	65.57	71.05
Child Mortality (Per 1000)	98.5(2012)	41.1(2013)	36.2(2013)	52.7(2013)	9.9 (2013)	41.6(2012)	85.5(2013)	9.6(2013)
% of under nourished	n.a.	16.3	n.a.	17	5.4	16	17.2	22.8

Source:- World Bank, 2016 & Statistics collected from various Government and Pvt. Firms

Table III shows that the per capita income of the 21% of the total Indian population is less than \$1.90 while, 58% manage only \$3.10 per day though India is the largest country in South Asia. Bangladesh and Nepal also has the same picture whereas, in Bhutan and Sri Lanka the situation is far better compared to the rest of the countries in this region. In case of Unemployment, Maldives tops the list with around 11.2% people still unemployed, followed by Afghanistan and Pakistan respectively. Even though only 3.6% of the Indian population is unemployed, there is severe scarcity of skilled labours in the Indian markets. Sri Lanka, India and Pakistan are the 3 most under nourished countries in the Southern Asia region and it shows the extent of poverty in these countries.

[5] Intrinsic Aspects of Poverty in South Asia

There are several intrinsic elements of poverty. These elements are the hidden agendas those are never highlighted holistically, but are the key causes of the phenomena.

Table - IV

Attributes	Afghanistan	Bangladesh	Bhutan	India	Maldives	Nepal	Pakistan	Sri Lanka
Income share held by highest 20%	n.a.	41.5	46.1	44	45	41.5	40.7	47
Income share held by fourth 20%	n.a.	21.2	21.4	20.6	21.9	21.9	21	20.5
Income share held by third 20%	n.a.	16	15	15.3	15.7	16.2	16.1	14.5
Income share held by second 20%	n.a.	12.5	10.8	11.9	11	12.1	12.8	10.8
Income share held by lowest 20%	n.a.	8.9	6.7	8.3	6.4	8.3	9.4	7.1

Source:- World Bank, 2016

[5.1] Inequality

The inequality reflects the gap between the wealth acquired by the different sections of the society. In this connection, South Asia's condition is substantially weak in term of income distribution. **Table - IV** indicates that almost in all the countries in South Asia the top 20% of the people acquire more than

40% of the total wealth in the country while the bottom 20% is held up with less than 9%. It means the gap in wealth accumulation is on an average 30-40% across all South Asian countries. Due to unequal wealth distribution the poor in this region finds it very difficult to move up the social ladder.

[5.2] Working Poor

It is a common belief that the unproductive or people having lack of proper skills or unwillingness to work are the only poor in a country but in countries like India, the largest group of poor living in rural areas are the agricultural cultivators or workers (**Gaiha, 1989**). Also, lack of employers stands as the major barrier give rise to educated unemployment.

[5.3] Lack of data

Often policies are made on the basis of macro data that in most of the times don't specify the magnitude of poverty on the micro level. There is a scarcity of micro data for almost all the countries of South Asia. Countries like Afghanistan, where the macro level data are not available, it is difficult to formulate any effective policy for these countries on world level.

[6] Tourism – A Way of Achieving Prosperity in South Asia: Country wise Tale

While giving an overall view on South Asian region, **Anwar (2012)** opines that the positive impacts of tourism development have brought prosperity which no doubt has ameliorated the quality of life of the people in this region by creating diverse economic opportunities. Tourism contributes significantly to 11 of the 12 nations that together account for 80 % of the world's poor including south Asian countries like Bangladesh, Nepal and Pakistan (MOPE: State of the Environment/Eco-Tourism/2004). **Islam (2008)** put slightly different opinion on **Bangladesh** i.e. “Due to lack of proper planning and research, Bangladesh is missing out on colossal amounts of revenue every year despite it has rich tourism potentials.”

The Nepalese community driven approach towards tourism development in **Nepal** including projects like Annapurna Tourism Development Project, Bhakthipur Conservation Project etc. emphasize on (a) Tourism benefits, (b) sense of ownership, (c) empowerment, (d) equity, (e) active participation in decision making process and (f) sustainable funding system.

Maldives, the tropical island country, known for its beautiful beaches, lagoons and reefs had the status of one of the twenty poorest countries in the world in 1980s but a rapid economic advancement in past few decades has upgraded this country into a middle-income country. According to World Bank, the share of population below poverty line shrunk from 23% to 15.7% in the time period from 2002 to 2009. Though the growth rate has been slowed down after 2004 Tsunami, it is expected to pick back up again before 2020. The economy of this nation is largely driven by tourism industry and its tourism business model is based on building strong partnerships with the overseas investors, tour operators and some of the best international and regional brand names. The tourism sector has

provided steady jobs and incomes for thousands of citizens and the economic growth and poverty alleviation have allowed Maldives to become one of the fastest developing nations in South Asia (Jacobsen, 2016).

Terrorism, 9/11 incident, issuance of negative travel advisories by western people were the few major factors responsible for the collapse of **Pakistan** tourism industry in last decade. But remarkable improvement in law and order and restoration of peace in recent time, have increased the foreign tourist flow compared to previous years. Recent studies reveal that tourism can bring social harmony in Pakistan. Not only that, it can contribute to the socio-economic development of rural Pakistan where most of the poor people actually live. Faizan Usmani, a Pakistani blogger supports it by saying that tourism can bring employment and economic benefit for everybody and if exploited meticulously and strategically, tourism entails a host of bright features for any depressed economy like ours by showering endless economic and financial fruits not only in any particular season but all throughout the year. **Nazar, Latif, Phulpoto, & Shaikh (2011)** reports that better tourism strategies has created employment opportunities for the local community and it has reduced poverty in districts like Shikarpur, Larkana, Sukkur and Jacobabad of Upper Sindh in Pakistan. On the eve of World Tourism Day 2013, the former Pakistan's Prime Minister, Nawaz Sharif officially acknowledged tourism's role in stimulating economic activity and poverty reduction on a high note. Pakistan Tourism Development Corporation (PTDC) also urged the World Bank to support Pakistan's tourism sector. Islamabad Chamber of Commerce and Industry (ICCI) urge the Pakistani diplomats to take necessary measures to project the country's tourism destinations over national and international media more aggressively. PTDC is now planning to develop tourist facilities and resorts along the CPEC corridor (China Pakistan Economic Corridor) with the purpose of poverty alleviation and it is expected that over 3 Million people will reap the benefit. The Pakistan Economy Watch (PEW) suggests that, "Pakistan government needs to turn tourism into a key driver for socio - economic development and poverty reduction" and for this purpose, "Pakistan needs to draw advantage from Chinese tourism industry, as the number Chinese travelling each year is expected to double by 2020 and they would be spending \$590 billion per annum."

International funding often plays a pivotal role in poverty alleviation but South Asian country like **Afghanistan** has witnessed a totally different experience. Even a strong economic growth backed by international spending, failed to put any significant impression in reducing poverty in this country during the time period from 2007-08 to 2011-12. The Afghanistan Poverty Status Update (jointly produced by the World Bank and the Government of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan's Ministry of Economy) reports that, four out of five poor people live in rural areas and more than 30% (one in three) Afghans even don't have sufficient money to cover basic needs. The Report also analyzes that international spending though helped the afghan economy to grow, but it hasn't equally benefited all sectors or specifically the poorest and as a result, the patterns of growth in Afghanistan have widened the gap between the rich and the poor. Therefore, USAID Office of Economic Growth (EGO) in

collaboration with Afghanistan Investment Support Agency (AISA) is trying to popularize tourism as a remedial tool to combat the poverty issue by (a) widening the scope of business opportunities in Afghanistan and (b) stimulating business interests in the USA to work with potential Afghan business partners.

Over the past ten years due to the progress in achieving Millennium Development Goals (MDG), social indicators in **Bhutan** have been improved but poverty still looms large in this country. 31% of rural population is poverty stricken people while in urban areas it is 1.7% of total urban population. Therefore, to combat poverty, Bhutan Government has taken few measures and one of them is giving special attention towards tourism. The country started projecting itself as an appealing tourism destination through television and internet since 1999. As a result, in 1974 Bhutan received only 287 visitors while, 7000 in 1999 (**Dorji, 2011**) and in 2016, approx. 209,570 international tourists visited Bhutan – a clear 9% growth in comparison with the previous year and the country earned almost 47.7 million US\$, its 10% of GDP! The United Nations Development Program (UNDP) in Bhutan has adopted the Gross National Happiness (GNH) to measure the wellbeing of nation and tourism has been considered as a key factor in mitigating the income differences. As the youth unemployment rate is rising day by day, the desire for more tourism is winning out. Therefore, Bhutan Government has also taken new tourism strategies such as (i) decentralize tourism development away from its capital city Thimphu, (ii) promote Bhutan as a year-round destination, (iii) make the unexplored areas more accessible by introducing air-connectivity and finally, (iv) adopt a tourism policy that can support sustainable development solve the issue like poverty.

In **India**, the Planning Commission, Govt. of India has praised the tourism sector many a time for its ability to create considerable number of job opportunities that can employ a wide spectrum of job seekers, even from its remote areas. According to **Dwivedi & Wadhwa (2016)**, India's travel and tourism sector is expected to be the second-largest employer in the world by 2019. Indian government has permitted 100 % FDI into all construction development and airport expansion projects. In addition scheme like 'tax holiday' for the time period of five years has also been offered to the organizations those set up tourism establishments at specific destinations (**Sharma, Johri & Chauhan, 2012**).

[7] Foreign Investment in South Asian Tourism in Recent Time

Arezki et al. (2009) finds out the linkage between the tourism growth and the growth in GDP (Gross Domestic Product). World Bank (2011), also advocates for international investments in tourism as it helps in tourism growth that benefits the local community especially the poor. As per IFC Report-2013, the International Finance Corporation has invested approx. 260 Million US\$ in different tourism projects in countries like **Bhutan, Maldives, Nepal and Sri Lanka**. The Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Sri Lankan tourism sector has created thousands of jobs in recent time. Many leading hotel chains also prefer this island country for their business expansion. The 2013, 4 billion

US\$ FDI project spearheaded by Singapore's Sri Lanka Gateway Industries Ltd created many direct and indirect jobs in this island country. Many FDI projects covering hospitality ventures are consuming large quantities of local non-human resources and these economic inputs are boosting Sri Lankan economy in a positive way that is also improving the standard of living in Sri Lanka and uplifting the poor involved in tourism or related businesses. **Maldives** has registered few foreign investments in tourism and the Economic Ministry has given license to 10 foreign investments in the first quarter of 2017 and most of these investments are in tourism sector.

In March, 2017, the World Bank has expanded its support for the poorest of **Pakistan** by approving a credit worth \$450 million, financed from International Development Association (IDA) and \$50 million has been sanctioned exclusively for the 'Punjab Tourism for Growth Project' to (i) give strength to the institutions, (ii) increase private sectors' engagement, (iii) revamp the tourism infrastructure in Punjab province, (iv) upgrade the existing service quality, (v) enhance opportunities for disadvantaged groups by conducting capacity building programmes, (vi) foster stronger governance and (vii) empower the host community with a special focus on women empowerment by unlocking more job scopes for them.

After realizing the tremendous marketability of rural **India**, UNDP with the collaboration of Union Tourism Ministry, India have launched endogenous tourism projects where, UNDP has funded approx. 2.5 million US\$ for the development and promotion of rural tourism, capacity building programmes for the rural people and participation of local NGOs, host community and local artisans. The World Bank Group is supporting Uttar Pradesh tourism on the 'Pro-Poor Tourism Development Programme' to develop Buddhist Circuits to increase tourist traffic and expand more economic opportunities for host communities.

[8] Select Tourism Initiatives towards Poverty Alleviation

[8.1] UNWTO ST-EP Programme

The UNWTO (United Nations World Tourism Organization) Sustainable Tourism – Eliminating Poverty(ST-EP) Programme, includes seven ST-EP mechanisms through which the underprivileged people can receive tangible benefits from tourism and poverty can be reduced up to 50% until 2015 (**Dimoska, 2008**). Since its inception in 2002, at the World Summit on Sustainable Development, Johannesburg, under this initiative, some 107 projects have been worked out up to 2013 time period in Least Developed Countries including the South Asian countries like Bhutan and Nepal.

[8.2] Tourism for Rural Poverty Alleviation Programme (TRPAP), Nepal

Ministry of Culture, Tourism and Civil Aviation funded by UNDP, SNV and DFID launched TRPAP, the successful pro-environment, pro-women and pro-rural communities program in 2001, across the

six districts in Nepal with an aim was alleviate poverty in Nepal through a 3 – level (Macro, Micro and Meso) sustainable rural tourism development model that would allow new tourism-product development and community participation at a larger scale. The project included home stay schemes, capacity building training programmes, marketing of local made products and environmental educational training like initiatives.

[8.3] Promoting Sustainable Tourism

The sustainable tourism can bring higher and faster economic development and therefore, it can be considered as a long term approach towards poverty elimination (**Dimoska, 2008**). In line with its mission to maximize the tourism benefits, UNWTO is relentlessly promoting the sustainable tourism in **Bhutan** since this country joined UNWTO in 2003. The neighboring country Nepal is also promoting tourism in a sustainable way. The ‘Sustainable Tourism Network’ in **Nepal** acts as a lobby platform that enhances the government support to achieve the goals of pro-poor tourism. **Anwar (2012)** studied over poverty alleviation through sustainable tourism in **Bangladesh** and he reveals that in Cox’s Bazar and St. Martin Island area the two most touristic places in Bangladesh, the contribution of sustainable tourism is immense in improving the general welfare of the local community as it has increased their income and purchasing power remarkably.

[8.4] Promoting Pro-Poor tourism

Many scholars argue that poverty alleviation can be possible by adopting Pro-Poor tourism a relatively new approach towards tourism development. World Bank, Asian Development Bank, International Monetary Fund like finance organizations those are giving support to tourism in many South Asian countries are consciously targeting the poor as an immediate approach to alleviate poverty. Canada, Australia, USA and New Zealand borne agencies are also working in many Pro-Poor tourism projects in countries like Nepal, Sri Lanka and India (**Anwar, 2012**).

[8.5] Increasing the Participation of Poor in Tourism

Lemma (2014) pointed out few challenges responsible for the limited access of poor in tourism in South Asian countries and how countries like Nepal, India have made remedial plans those influence the participation in the tourism sector by the poor.

Challenges	Remedial Plan
Lack of Government Support	SNV has posted 2 permanent staffs in 'Nepalese Tourism Board' to strengthen its government capacity that can play more proactive role in involving the poor in tourism.
Lack of Organizational Strength	SNV's District Partner Programme (DPP) helps the local NGOs to run social mobilization programmes on the trekking routes of Nepal.
Inadequate Financial Capital	SNVs District Partner Programme (DPP) offers a 'Venture Capital Fund' which provides loans using group, rather than individual, collateral.
Insufficient Human Capital	In the year of 2009, The Ministry of Tourism (MOT), GoI, launched a special initiative, a 6 to 8 weeks training programme (free of cost) in the name of 'Hunar Se Rozgar Tak' Programme (HSRT) to create employable skills amongst the youth.
Gender Norms & Constraints	The Nepalese NETIF initiative provides microcredit for women to set up their own micro-enterprises. The Kerala RTI also provides funding and training for women in order to improve their inclusiveness in the sector.

In an interview, in 2005, Agha Iqrar Haroon, the founder of Ecotourism Society Pakistan (ESP) said that unless the involvement of local mountain communities at grass-root level would be possible in Pakistan; promoting tourism by different means or "chanting slogans for the rights of people cannot provide bread to a poor man." Therefore, Ecotourism Society Pakistan is working on the area of community participation and to ensure that local communities must have their direct share in revenue generated by tourism. In Nepal, The Nepal Environment and Tourism Initiative Foundation (NETIF) is running a "multiannual, multidimensional, pro-poor tourism initiative" that emphasizes on the implementation of responsible tourism certification initiatives and local business promotion.

[8.6] Community Based Tourism (CBT)

CBT offers considerable opportunities for marginal communities to participate in the tourism industry (Spenceley & Meyer, 2012). Pearce (1992) suggests that CBT provides a mechanism for an equitable flow of benefits to all tourism stakeholders, through a system of local development control and consensus-based decision making. Treslian (2006) studied over the experience of Community Based Ecotourism Development for poverty alleviation projects in Central and South Asia (from 2002 to 2005) and he concludes that if CBT projects will promote environmentally and socially responsible tourism products; conduct capacity building programme for especially youth and women from local community and if local producers, suppliers, artisans and performers would be encouraged to market their local cultural activities and events; it can "increase per capita income and establish a solid tourism revenue stream and strengthen community based and civil society organisations at project sites". The NETIF (Nepal Environment and Tourism Initiative Foundation) provides

assistance in the start-up of Community Based Tourism enterprises and micro-infrastructure. The Community-Based Tourism in Bhutan has boosted the regional incomes by enabling the host community to supply locally produced food to hotels and travelers and selling locally-made handicrafts in tourist souvenir shops located in prominent tourism spots. The huge tourist traffic during its major religious festivals also feeds great amount of revenue into its local economies every year.

[8.7] Ecotourism

Ecotourism, often considered as Responsible Holiday Travel to natural sites with having dual objectives a) Conservation of Nature and b) Improve well-being of host community, is increasing by 20% per annum (**Rasul & Manandhar, 2009**). Countries like Bhutan, Nepal have already formulated and published their individual 'National Ecotourism Strategy'. Annapurna Conservation Area in Nepal is a good example of women's empowerment through ecotourism project. Ecotourism has become an effective tool to solving problems like poverty in mountain/tribal areas of Pakistan. **Saville (2002)** finds out the tremendous potentiality of ecotourism in the Tamil Nadu region of India, where there are multiple synergies to create eco-tourism products those are also pro-poor.

[8.8] Agri Tourism

ILO 'Toolkit on Poverty Reduction through Tourism' - 2013 reports that "while the agriculture sector is becoming more difficult and less profitable industry for the majority of the Indian population, Agri Tourism Development Corporation has developed a concept that is leading the way towards sustainable livelihoods for many farmers and their families." Agri Tourism Development Corporation (ATDC), India, facilitates the rural farmers of Maharashtra, to make their livelihood secured by diversifying business opportunities. ATDC also provides employment to the rural youth in its centers and provides contractual jobs to the village-women through organized Women Self-Help Groups.

[8.9] Supply of Goods & Services by the Poor or by the Enterprises Employing the Poor

Sadrudin (2014) suggests that if the poor can sale and/or supply goods directly in the market it will be one of the best approaches to meet the issue of poverty as it will boost the informal economy. Tiger Tops Mountain Travel, Nepal actively purchases products from the local producers at its lodges in Pokhara. During Sindh Festival 2014 in Pakistan, the local producers from the rural areas were invited to market their products to the visitors, representing the local and global community. Travel Walji's Limited (TWL), Pakistan's largest Inbound Tour Operator, is rigorously promoting Karimbad, located in the Karakorum region, where this tour operator is supporting the local entrepreneurs to set up their own businesses. As a result, now there are now 27 shops selling handicrafts, trekking equipment, food staffs etc. and more than 70 small family-owned hotels providing income to the local poor people.

[8.10] Private Sector Participation for Bringing about Sustainable Tourism Growth

UNWTO and ILO (International Labour Organization) both have advocated for the involvement of private sectors such as individual enterprises as well as the development banks and development finance institutions like International Finance Corporation (IFC) in tourism development for

harnessing the power of tourism in case of poverty alleviation in South Asia. With the end of nearly 30 years' civil war, the North and the East Sri Lanka – home to a treasure trove of unexplored assets, are now open for tourists. IFC and National Geographic are working together to bring sustainable tourism growth to these regions by promoting their unique natural, historic and cultural assets identified by the local stakeholders. More than ever, such initiative has connected the local community with tourism that enables them to thrive benefits from it.

[8.11] Marketing Assistance to the Enterprises for Sustainable Tourism Practices

Marketing Assistance to Nepal for Sustainable Tourism Products initiative (MAST) a joint venture by SNV and UNEP, on the concept of sustainable tourism practices allows the tourism enterprises to capture the European tourist market with an increasing demand for sustainable tourism products. By strengthening sustainable tourism in Nepal, this project has maximized the economic benefits to the poor and minimized the socio-cultural and environmental cost of tourism at a destination. (UNEP/UNDP, NTB, SNV, EU, 2008 Annual Report).

[8.12] Market Linkages between Tourism Enterprises and the Local / National Economy

Poverty reduction depends on how well-linked tourism enterprises are with the local enterprises both at formal and informal level (UNCTAD, 2013). Investments by the private sectors, even if may not seem to be pro-poor in initial days may create larger pro-poor effect through employment and local market links in later period of time. In this connection, **Hoermann et al. (2010)** explained that value chain analysis in the context of Himalayan tourism in South Asia to understand how tourism activities can be better implemented in order to increase the share of tourism expenditure that goes towards the poor within the region. According to him if the poor will understand what sort of employment opportunities exist in the tourism value chain, it will obviously be beneficial for the poor as it will help them to find out alternative source of earning to earn more that can reduce the poverty level in a larger way. Kerala Responsible Tourism Initiative (Kerala RTI) was set up by the local government, that shifted the way in which local hotels sourced their food production by setting up partnerships with the local farmers and the food suppliers (UNCTAD, 2013).

[9] CONCLUSION

By analysing the various facets of poverty in South Asia the paper highlights the fact that even after many measures taken at national and international level, poverty stands as the biggest challenge for development in South Asia and its roots and undeniably strong. The region has shown a lot of progression in tourism development in the last decade and continues to grow at a much faster rate than any other region in the world. The paper concludes that, tourism, as one of the emerging sectors in the world have shown much progression in alleviating poverty in countries like Maldives, Sri Lanka, Nepal and to some extent India. However, much needs to be done for countries like Pakistan and

Afghanistan where poverty is rampant and the nation is blessed with both natural and artificial manifests supporting tourism development.

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